

Design and synthesis of NSAIDs derivatives as antioxidant agents

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Abstract : An extensive literature review reveals that various NSAIDs, their analogues and hybrids possess anticancer¹ and antioxidant¹⁻³ properties. The present study aims at designing, docking studies and synthesis of drug hybrids of NSAIDs with other amino compounds linked through dipeptide spacers, which are known for their anticancer as well as cellular penetrating properties. The synthesis was carried out by solution phase method using 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) or *o*-(benzotriazol-1-yl)-*N,N,N',N'*-tetramethyluronium tetrafluoroborate (TBTU) as coupling reagent and triethyl amine (TEA) as a base in chloroform. Antioxidant studies showed that the synthesized NSAID derivatives showed moderate antioxidant activity as compared to the standard, ascorbic acid.

Keywords : NSAIDs, anticancer, antioxidant, EDC, TBTU, triethyl amine.

Introduction

NSAIDs are most widely used therapeutic agents known to suppress the inflammatory response, pain and lower the elevated body temperature. They are mostly heterogeneous aromatic compounds of which most widely used drugs are aspirin, ibuprofen, aceclofenac and diclofenac. NSAIDs act by inhibiting the COX enzymes which catalyze the biosynthesis of prostaglandins responsible for inflammatory response.

Recent research showed that NSAIDs even have antioxidant, cytostatic and antiviral activities. Amide derivatives of NSAIDs showed good antioxidant¹⁻³, anti-cholesterolemic and antihyperlipidemic activity with reduced GI toxicity⁴. Some modulating effects of NSAIDs showed DNA fragmentation activity⁵ which is related to antineoplastic activity^{1,5,6} and some showed reduced ulcerogenic effect of amide derivatives of NSAIDs⁴.

In the present study NSAIDs (Diclofenac, Aceclofenac) were coupled with various amino acids to get the amide derivatives and evaluated for their antioxidant scavenging activity by DPPH method taking ascorbic acid as the standard. The NSAIDs and amino acids selected were based on the docking studies taking the various combinations of NSAIDs and amino acids with target proteins causing skin cancer induced by solar UV radiation with PDB ID : 3SA0.

Materials and methods :

Materials :

The reagents which are commercially available and the analytical grade solvents were used without any further purification. All the reactions were conducted in dried apparatus to maintain anhydrous condition. The reactions were stirred magnetically unless stated otherwise. Amino acids, di-tert-butylpyrocarbonate, trifluoroacetic acid, EDC and TBTU were obtained from Spectrochem Ltd., Mumbai. DPPH, diethyl ether, methanol and chloroform was obtained from AVRA. IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrometer using a thin film support on KBr pellets. The values are reported as ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR spectra was recorded on Bruker (400 MHz) NMR spectrometer. The spectra were obtained in CDCl₃ and the chemical shift values are reported as values in ppm ($\delta = 0$). GC-MS spectra were recorded. The protection of amino and carboxyl group and their deprotection were done by standard procedures⁷⁻⁹.

Docking study :

A preliminary docking study was done on all the NSAIDs hybrids using Molegro Virtual Docker software. All the hybrids were docked on target proteins causing skin cancer induced by solar UV radiation with PDB ID : 3SA0.

Synthesis of peptide and NSAIDs hybrids :

Amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride (10 mmol) was dissolved in chloroform (20 ml), to this solution TEA (4 ml) was added and stirred for 15 min. Boc-amino acid (10 mmol) in chloroform (CHCl₃) (20 ml) and TBTU or EDC (10 mmol) were added with stirring. After completion of reaction, the resulting mixture was washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate (20 ml), 5% HCl (20 ml) and distilled H₂O respectively. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was evaporated over water bath and recrystallized using chloro-

form and ether.

The above procedure was also followed for coupling amino acid ester and dipeptide with NSAIDs, i.e. Diclofenac (Scheme 1) and Aceclofenac (Scheme 2).

Antioxidant activity :

The synthesized hybrids of NSAIDs were evaluated for antioxidant activity using 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) method¹⁰. In this method, a stable free radical was formed whose absorbance was measured at 517 nm, the absorbance is inversely proportional to the antioxidant activity. To 3 ml of the synthesized sample, 1

Scheme 1. Synthetic scheme Diclofenac-valine-OMe (DV), Diclofenac-leucine-OMe (DL) and Diclofenac-valine-leucine-OMe (DVL).

Scheme 2. Synthetic scheme of Aceclofenac-valine-OMe (AV), Aceclofenac-leucine-OMe (AL) and Aceclofenac-valine-leucine-OMe (AVL).

ml of 0.1 N methanolic solution of DPPH was added and kept in dark for 30 min and the absorbance was measured using JASCO V-760 spectrometer. Methanol was used as a blank and ascorbic acid as the standard.

Results and discussion

Docking studies :

A prior study was done by coupling the NSAIDs with several amino acids on target proteins causing skin cancer induced by solar UV radiation with PDB ID : 3SA0 and the docking scores obtained were shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Docking study of ligands on 3SA0 (skin cancer receptor)

Sr. no.	Ligand	Dock score
1.	DV	-120
2.	DL	-106
3.	DVL	-118
4.	AV	-123
5.	AL	-134
6.	AVL	-132

Synthesis :

The synthesis of all the hybrids was carried out by solution phase technique and the results of the hybrids along with the physical properties are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Physical data of the NSAIDs hybrids

Sr. no.	Compounds	Nature	% of Yield
1.	DV	Semisolid	61.3
2.	DL	Semisolid	55.4
3.	DVL	Semisolid	52.4
4.	AV	Semisolid	45.6
5.	AL	Semisolid	48.6
6.	AVL	Semisolid	35.8

Spectral analysis :

Diclofenac-Val-Leu-OMe (DVL) : Yield 52.4%; light brown semisolid; IR spectrum (ν/cm^{-1}) : 3313.71 cm^{-1} , (NH stretch), 2962.66 cm^{-1} (Alip-CH stretch), 3066.82 cm^{-1} (Ar-CH stretch), 1732.08 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch); ^1H NMR spectrum (δ , ppm) : 7.524 (1H, d, Ar-CH), 7.217 (1H, m, Ar-CH), 3.719 (2H, d, CH_2), 4.202 (1H, s, Alip-CH), 2.077 (14H, m, CH_2), 0.873 (6H, d, CH_3); the molecular ion peak was obtained at 519 (M+2).

Aceclofenac-Val-OMe (AV) : Yield 45.6%; light brown

semisolid; IR spectrum (ν/cm^{-1}) : 3324.71 cm^{-1} (NH stretch), 2978.56 cm^{-1} (Alip-CH stretch), 3057.82 cm^{-1} (Ar-CH stretch), 1742.08 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch); ^1H NMR spectrum (δ , ppm) : 7.624 (1H, d, Ar-CH), 7.372 (1H, m, Ar-CH), 3.814 (2H, d, CH_2), 4.202 (1H, s, Alip-CH), 2.1 (14H, m, CH_2), 0.893 (6H, d, CH_3); the molecular ion peak was obtained at 465 (M+1).

Antioxidant study :

All the NSAIDs derivatives exhibited moderate to good antioxidant activities as compared to the standard, ascorbic acid. Table 3 illustrates the scavenging ability of prepared sample and standards.

Table 3. Antioxidant activity of the synthesized ligands

Ligands	% Scavenging activity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		
	25	50	100
Standard	35.26	57.45	77.1
DV	27.63	42.68	62.68
DL	20.14	31.3	45.65
DVL	29.16	43.04	63.8
AV	23.67	40.56	51.8
AL	26.4	43.1	58.2
AVL	24.7	45.2	60.3

Conclusion

The synthesis of drug hybrids of NSAIDs with other amino compounds linked through amino acids and dipeptide spacers was successfully carried out by solution phase technique. Docking of the synthesized ligands on target proteins causing skin cancer induced by solar UV radiation with PDB ID : 3SA0, showed similar properties related to anticancer agents. The ligands exhibited moderate antioxidant activity and expected to have anticancer activity.

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